

Influence of seedling age on rice yield

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During 1979 sornavari and samba seasons, the performance of short- and medium-duration rice varieties was studied in relation to seedling age in sandy loam soils of PES, Tirurkuppam. The previous finding that 25-day-old seedlings are best had to be confirmed with reference to different soil and agro-climatic regions. Short-duration (ADT31 and TKM9) and medium-duration varieties (IR20 and ASDIS) at four seedling ages were tested. Sprouted seeds

Grain yield of short- and medium-duration varieties at 4 seedling ages during 2 seasons in 1979. PES, Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India.

Season and variety	Grain yield (t/ha) of seedlings aged				CD (P = 0.05)
	25 d	30 d	35 d	40 d	
<i>Sornavari</i>					
ADT31	3.87	4.05	4.22	4.42	
TKM9	4.16	4.60	5.26	5.70	0.8
<i>Samba</i>					
IR20	3.02	3.24	3.30	3.37	
ASD15	2.82	2.91	2.98	3.02	N.S.

were treated with diammonium phosphate 3%.

The yield differences between seedling ages were significant for both the short- and medium-duration varieties (see table). In the short-duration group, ADT31 recorded yields similar for all seedling ages. The yield trend favored older seedlings. In TKM9, the 40- and

35-day-old seedlings recorded higher yields than the 30- and 25-day-old seedlings. In the medium-duration group, the yield differences among the seedling ages were not significant. Thus, seedlings of short- and medium-duration rice varieties up to 40 days of age can be planted to advantage in sandy loam soils. ■

Seed rate and spacing for the rice crop

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The influence of seed rate in wet nursery and spacing on rice grain yield was studied during 1979 sornavari and samba seasons at PES, Tirurkuppam. Previous studies have shown that increasing or decreasing the seed rate beyond 3 kg/40 m² resulted in low yields. The study also aimed to keep the yields high at higher seed rates per unit area by nitrogen (N) placement in the crop (TKM9). The treatments consisted of four seed rates, three times of placement, and two spacings (see table). The N placement in the main field was 75 kg N/ha, given 15, 20, and 25 days after planting in a single dose. Phosphorus and potassium were applied as basal doses as recommended by soil tests.

Results showed that the seed rate of 3 kg/40 m² was optimum. The seedlings raised at that rate had optimum physiological growth conducive to higher yields. It was also observed that the grain yield of crops planted at

Influence of seed rate, nitrogen placement, and plant spacing on grain yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1979 sornavari	1979 samba
<i>Seed rates</i>		
1.0 kg/m ² – Pai nursery	5.87	3.60
1.5 kg/40m ² – field nursery	6.40	3.61
3.0 kg/40m ² – field nursery	6.71	3.91
6.0 kg/40m ² – field nursery	6.02	3.50
CD = (P = 0.05)	0.55	0.24
<i>N placement</i>		
75 kg N/ha 15 DT	6.35	3.61
75 kg N/ha 20 DT	6.18	3.73
75 kg N/ha 25 DT	6.22	3.64
CD = (P = 0.05)	NS	NS
<i>Spacings</i>		
20 x 10	6.44	3.97
20 x 20 cm	6.07	3.34
CD = (P = 0.05)	NS	0.17

^aDT = days after transplanting.

different seed rates was not affected by N applications. The closer spacing of 20 × 10 cm or 50 hills/m² gave higher

yields, which appeared to be optimum for all short-duration varieties like TKM9 (105 days). ■

Growth of azolla with rice and its effect on rice yield

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Azolla is a useful green manure crop. Its nitrogen-fixing activity is due to an endophytic blue-green alga. When azolla is continuously cropped, it can produce molecular nitrogen of as much

as 500 kg/ha annually. In the rice field, azolla growth is fast at the rice crop's early stage, but declines later because of shading by the rice canopy. Widening the distance between rice plant rows will allow the growing of azolla during the whole growth period of wetland rice. This technique was tried experimentally in China.

At IRRI, rice was grown in a 35-m² plot in a wide-narrow row spacing.

Wide rows spaced 53 cm alternated with narrow rows 13.6 cm apart. The distance between hills in 1 row was 6.6 cm.

Fresh azolla (*A. pinnata*) amounting to 13-18 kg was inoculated into a plot. A total of 53 kg superphosphate/ha was applied — half before transplanting and the rest at the time of each azolla inoculation. All plots were supplied with equal amounts of phosphate. Carbofuran (3% a.i.) at 1 g/m² was broadcast on the azolla inoculum.

After 15 to 20 days, azolla covered the paddy water surface. The water was drained for 2-3 days to make the azolla adhere to the soil surface. Then the azolla was incorporated into the soil by feet, hand weeder, or rake. A fresh

inoculum was applied with superphosphate and insecticide. This allowed azolla to grow 4-6 times during one crop of rice. In the second trial azolla was not grown after rice had headed because the paddy surface was shaded and azolla growth was poor.

To study the effect of azolla incorporation, three treatments — no nitrogen, with chemical nitrogen, and with azolla — were compared (see table). Ammonium sulfate was applied before transplanting and incorporated into the soil. The plots were arranged in a Latin square.

The response of the first rice crop to azolla incorporation was apparent only at late stages of growth. No yield increase from azolla incorporation was

observed probably because soil fertility was high. In the second crop rice growth in the early stage was better in azolla-treated plots than in no-nitrogen plots because of the carry-over of nitrogen from the previous azolla crop.

In the third rice crop, some plots were severely affected by boron toxicity. The toxicity was more severe in chemical nitrogen plots — hence yields were lower — than in azolla-treated plots.

In the fourth trial, plot size was 49 m² and distance between hills in 1 row was 13 cm. The average for four trials indicated that growing several crops of azolla in wide rows under a rice canopy and incorporating them gave about 1-t grain yield increase over the 0-nitrogen control. ■

Comparison of grain yields of azolla-treated plots and of plots with and without chemical nitrogen. IRRI, 1978-80.

Trial sequence	Cropping duration (from transplanting to harvest) and variety	Chemical nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Azolla incorporations (no.) and nitrogen content	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
				0 nitrogen	Chemical nitrogen	Azolla
1st	Dec 1978-Apr 1979 121 days IR26	107	6 crops, 105 kg N/ha	6.3 a	8.3 a	6.7 a
2d	May-Aug 1979 124 days IR42	60	4 crops, 70 kg N/ha	3.7 b	4.5 b	5.7 a
3d	Nov 1979-Mar 1980 104 days IR42	100	4 crops, 70 kg N/ha	2.7 b	2.2 b	3.6 a
4th ^b	Feb-Jun 1980 121 days IR42	60	4 crops, 70 kg N/ha	5.2 b	6.2 a	6.2 a

^a Any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level. ^b Field is different from the previous ones. One crop of azolla was grown before transplanting. Plant density was half that in the previous trials.

Environment and its influence

Supply of dry matter from stems to grain in rice grown under dryland conditions

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Studies on locally grown cereals show that flowering occurs about halfway through the crop's growth period in

maize and wheat but relatively later in rice, with grain development taking up a much smaller proportion of the growth period.

The relatively short grain-filling period in rice suggests either that good grain yields result from an accelerated crop growth rate after flowering, coincident with the development of the grain sink, or that substantial stored dry matter from other plant parts is translocated to

the grain during grain filling.

Three varieties, Blue Belle, IR40, and Brazos, which grow well in local dryland conditions, were sampled every 2 weeks for growth analysis.

In all the three varieties, crop growth rate reached a maximum at panicle emergence and decreased soon thereafter. In maize and wheat, crop growth rate reaches a maximum some weeks after anthesis.